

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NZAU****FIRST NAME: FRANCISCA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: DR.GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MSWord-Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the Writing style adopted by Euclid University?

- Chicago Rules of Style.¹**
- APA publication manual.
- Wikipedia.
- English style guide
- What is the importance of citing sources?

2. What is the importance of citing sources?

- To quote the source of the information.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 34-35.

- To provide general information.
 - To adopt other researchers' work as their own.
 - To include in an Essay writing.
3. Why develop a plan for Dissertation writing?
- To help to set achievable goals while writing.**³
 - To gain speed in the drafting of ideas.
 - To give an overview of the research.
 - To have ideas flowing.
4. What is an examples part of a Ph.D. dissertation?
- Literature Review.**⁴
 - Sentences.
 - English Language.
 - Paragraphs.
5. What is the meaning of pure research?
- Research that answers conceptual problems.**⁵
 - Research that answers practical problems.
 - The research was done in a controlled environment.

³ Kate L. Turabian. *A manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*: Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 76.

⁴ Turabian, *Manual for Writers*, 111.

⁵ Turabian, *Manual for writers*, 22.

- Research is done by Corporates.
6. What purpose does the European Central Bank serve?
- To maintain purchasing power of the Euro Currency.**⁶
- To pay for the imports into all the European Union countries.
- To ration the amount of currency in circulation.
- To give loans to the European Member states.
7. What purpose does the English style serve to the European Union?
- For departmental memos or papers for specialist committees.**⁷
- To write laws of the members' countries.
- To prepare thousands of documents written in and translated into English.
- To shun away the use of American English.
8. What are the critical components of the Methodology chapter?
- Research Design.**⁸
- Unethical considerations.
- Quantitative Research.
- Qualitative Research.

⁶ European Commission. *A handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (Luxemburg: European Commission, 2021), 94.

⁷ European Commission, *A handbook for Authors and Translators*, 4.

⁸ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing your qualitative Dissertation: A Road-map from beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2018), 433.

9. What constitutes a good recommendation?

- By being logically and clearly derived from the findings.**⁹
- Mere restatements of the findings from research.
- Interpretations of the entire Dissertation.
- Theories quoted in the study.

10. Why undertake Literature Review in a Dissertation?

- It relates to the problem statement, purpose, and research questions.**¹⁰
- It reviews primary sources written over ten years ago.
- To copy what has been tested by other researchers.
- To build on what others have started.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your qualitative Dissertation*, 680.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your qualitative Dissertation*, 77.

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